

Research on the effectiveness of covid vaccines and cognitive death of empiricism in medicine

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Abstract

With the covid crisis, medical science has lost the spirit of empiricism. Articles are published about the effectiveness of vaccines, which do not have a relevant mathematical model and exclude the fact that only a control group of an unvaccinated part of the population can prove the effectiveness of vaccination against covid. Using elementary school math, we can calculate the death rate of a vaccinated subset of the population and compare it to the death rate of an unvaccinated subset of the population. No one has made this simple and effective calculation.

Keywords: covid vaccination, mortality rate, statistics.

The spirit of empirical science born in the Renaissance is one of the brightest achievements of Mankind. It has taken the human race out of the dark early middle age of irrationality and superstition. The core of empiricism is the development of a mathematical description of the world that is verified with the experiment. Here is the cognitive power of empiricism that has intuitively chosen the bijective research methodology as its basic rule. In Newton's physics, every element in the mathematical model of the world has exactly one corresponding element in physical reality. For example, the formula for gravitational force between two physical objects:

$$F_g = \frac{m_1 \cdot m_2 \cdot G}{r^2},$$

where we have mass one, mass two, distance r between masses, and gravitational constant that was precisely measured by Cavendish and later by other physicists. Empirical science has linked physical reality and a model of physical reality to the extent of objectivity. When we say that science is objective, we mean that what science says, is true in its physical actuality.

We have several articles published in peer review journals that claim covid vaccines decreased mortality rate, and that with covid vaccination millions of lives were saved. When you read these articles, you see that there is no empirical bond between the mathematical model and the physical reality. Authors are claiming that covid vaccines helped the vaccinated part of the population and saved numerous lives, but nobody is comparing the mortality rate of the vaccinated part of the population with the mortality rate of the non-vaccinated part of the population. This comparison is the most reliable statistical method that respects the spirit of empirical science.

The effectiveness of a given medicine we can measure at the best of the people that did not receive the medicine. Claiming that covid vaccines have reduced the mortality of the vaccinated part of the population and that the unvaccinated part of the population has a higher death rate, without measuring it, is an unprecedented cognitive decline of empirical science.

If we really want to know the real effectiveness of covid vaccines this can be done by the primary school knowledge of mathematics. We calculate the mortality rate (MR) for the years 2021 and 2022 of both groups (vaccinated and non-vaccinated) in percentages:

$$MR_{vaccinated} = \frac{100 \cdot vaccinated\ dead}{vaccinated}$$

$$MR_{non-vaccinated} = \frac{100 \cdot non-vaccinated\ dead}{non-vaccinated}$$

Using this mathematical model, both groups would be equally examined and this is the only way to get objective results. According to the official narrative the mortality rate $MR_{vaccinated}$ should be much lower than the mortality rate $MR_{non-vaccinated}$. But nobody did this simple and empirically 100% accurate calculus.

Using advanced statistics, we divide the population into five age groups (0-20, 21-40, 41-60, 61-80, and above 80).

Age group	Dead D	Alive	Vaccinated
0-20 (1)	D1	A1	V1
21-40 (2)	D2	A2	V2
41-60 (3)	D3	A3	V3
61-80 (4)	D3	A4	V4
+80 (5)	D5	A5	V5

The exact mortality rate for each age group we calculate as follows:

$$VD_{Proportional} = \frac{Vn \cdot Dn}{An},$$

where $VD_{proportional}$ is the proportional number of vaccinated dead persons. According to our results the calculated $VD_{proportional}$ is always smaller than the statistical number of vaccinated dead persons $VD_{statistical}$, which means that covid vaccines increased mortality rate.

How it has happened that these articles passed the so-called “peer review”? I leave it to the historians of science. One thing is already clear, with the covid crisis, “The spirit of empirical science in medicine has died”. Peer review in medicine is replaced with “Big Pharma Review”. With the beginning of covid crisis, the life philosophy of empathy for humans and life is replaced with globalist anti-life philosophy that is “anti-human” and “anti-life” oriented. Its representative is Yuval Noah Harari, who denies the existence of the Spirit (Being, Consciousness). For him, we humans are only biological machines, that should be improved

with genetic engineering and nanotechnology. Globalists put their ego in front of God. Globalism is an “Anti-Christ philosophy” which threatens to destroy human civilization.

Academic, Prof. Dr. Krešimir Pavelić from Croatia is clear: if we want to protect public health worldwide, the first step is to disable the World Health Organization (WHO) to have any impact on health policy, which means cancelling the membership. WHO should take care only of their personnel, for the personnel of the World Economic Forum and personnel of Big Pharma. In this way, they will do their maximum to protect public health worldwide.

Sources:

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